
USING PODCASTS FOR ENHANCING LISTENING SKILLS

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Abstract: Listening and speaking are fundamental communication skills. Language learners who study a foreign language need to learn these skills seriously to communicate well. Unfortunately, learning those skills is difficult for them. As podcasts have many benefits for the students, those resources help students to learn the language. The paper discussed how podcasts are helpful for foreign language learners to improve their listening and speaking skills. This literature review indicated several previous studies recommending using podcasts as learning support in improving listening and speaking skills.

Keywords: Podcasts, listening skills, speaking skills.

Listening to a variety of topics - from science and technology to history and pop-culture - he became engrossed in podcasts, and they proved to be the missing tool in his learning journey. Farhan explains, "Podcasts force you to become a more active listener. Unlike movies, TV series, or YouTube videos, podcasts demand complete focus on audio. This can help develop your concentration and reduce distractions in your environment. By actively listening to podcasts, you can better your capacity to pay attention to what others are saying."

In fact, podcasts are more effective as a learning tool, as they usually feature natural and conversational language compared to movies and TV series, which often

include scripted and rehearsed dialogue. In contrast, podcasts typically present unscripted conversations between hosts and guests, making it easier for learners to pick up on natural English expressions, slang, and idioms commonly used in real-life conversations. Farhan states, "You will get an immersive language experience through podcasts. Since they are audio-only, you are forced to rely solely on your listening to understand the discussion. It demands active engagement for better comprehension."

One of the most significant advantages of listening to podcasts is that it makes learning English an engaging and enjoyable experience, unlike traditional language-learning methods that can be dry and tedious. Furthermore, podcasts are more accessible than movies and TV series, as you can listen to them on your mobile devices or computers at any time, making learning easier to fit into your busy schedules. In contrast, movies and TV series require a more significant time commitment, which can be challenging to fit into your routine.

Podcasts offer a convenient and time-efficient way to improve English skills, as they can be listened to while doing other activities like cooking, exercising, or commuting to university or work. Listening to podcasts exposes you to a range of voices and accents, helping you become more comfortable with different dialects and accents, which is crucial in today's globalized world where you interact with people from different cultures and backgrounds.

Moreover, podcasts can improve your listening comprehension, as many are designed to challenge listeners with complex vocabulary, idiomatic expressions, and fast-paced dialogue. Listening to these podcasts can improve your ability to understand spoken English, pick up on subtle nuances, and cultural references.

Here is a list of podcasts you can check out: Revisionist History with Malcolm Gladwell: A podcast that re-examines overlooked or misunderstood events and ideas from history. Revisionist History provides English learners with an opportunity to improve their listening and comprehension skills while learning about interesting

and thought-provoking topics. Malcolm Gladwell and his guests have fun chats, tell interesting stories and ask difficult questions.

BBC Global News Podcast: A daily news podcast that covers the latest events and trends from around the world. BBC Global News Podcast exposes English learners to a variety of topics and vocabulary related to current events, as well as, different accents and dialects of English.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION :Podcasts in Learning Process Podcasting is one of the digital technology tools that is useful as a supporting tool in a learning process. Podcasting is one of the new, useful and interesting tools that can be used inside and outside of class by learners and teachers to advance and discharge educational elements and contents and to help and encourage learners to learn foreign languages better, Shafiee, F., & Salehi, H. (2019). This tool can help teachers to improve their teaching performance in the class and can develop learning activities as well. On the student side, the technology promotes the student's attitude towards learning, (Nova, M., 2022:39). The use of podcasts in tertiary education is considered to promote motivation and engagement, cognition and learning, learner autonomy and innovative opportunities for teaching and presenting (Salmon & Nie, 2008 in Phillips, B. (2017:159). Bustari, A., Samad, I. A., & Achmad, D. (2017:99) claimed that podcast media affirmatively shows good point for students in case of it would bring the students closer to the target language, and it affects students' attitude and motivation. It is supported by Rahimi & Katal, 2012 in Shafiee, F., & Salehi, H. (2019), they stated that learners can use podcasts for various aims such as replacing classroom presentations, adding more materials for classroom teachings, and increasing creativity, innovativeness and cooperation among students. Furthermore, podcasting can be a very powerful tool to increase class interaction and foster collaborative learning by developing the skills needed to work towards a shared goal, (Phillips, B. 2017: 161).

Podcast for Listening and Speaking Skills. As a digital recording, podcasts can be used to support English language learning, specifically on the listening skill, (Indahsari, D., 2020:103). It is supported by Sartika D.H (2020:891), she said that podcast is an alternative teaching media to support students' Listening Skill. These programs are generally conducted by someone or people who manage a conversation, do stories telling or share stories, or provide information to the media. As Bamanger, E. M., & Alhassan, R. A. (2015:66) stated that those resources provide students the opportunity to experience authentic forms of the language and get personal involvement to learn various skills in the language of English. They contain the original speech of the native speakers. Hence, language learners can listen to the original speech sound and learn to pronounce and speak the target language from the native sources, and help them improve their listening and speaking skills. As Yaman, I. (2016:64) stated, that as podcasts consist of audio and video files, they constitute an invaluable tool that contributes to the development of listening and pronunciation skills, especially in foreign language learning contexts it is hard to access authentic materials but podcasts remove this barrier through original speech, dialogues, radio and TV programs, etc.

In conclusion: Podcasts are an effective tool for enhancing listening skills due to their diverse content and real-life conversations. By exposing listeners to various topics, accents, and conversational styles, podcasts help improve comprehension and engagement.

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